

THE CONSTITUENTS OF *DIDYMOCARPUS PEDICELLATA*. PART III. ISOLATION OF A SESQUITERPENE AND TWO POLYTERPENE PRODUCTS AND EXA- MINATIO OF THE FATTY MATTER.

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A sesquiterpene, didymocarpene, has been isolated from the essential oil of the leaves. From the heavier essential oil fraction two terpenic products, didymocarpol ($C_{50}H_{100}O_5$) and didymocarpenol ($C_{25}H_{42}O$) have been isolated and characterised. These two products have also been isolated from the unsaponifiable matter in the non-volatile, fatty residue. The saturated saponification acids are found to consist of palmitic, stearic, behenic and lignoceric acids in nearly equal proportions. Free stearic acid is also found to be present in the leaves.

The process of isolation of pedicin and three other allied colouring matters (Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 12, 703) from the ethereal extract of the leaves of *Didymocarpus pedicellata* entailed the simultaneous separation of (a) an essential oil, (b) a neutral, and (c) an acid fraction. The present paper deals with the investigation of these three fractions, which together form the main bulk of the total ethereal extract and from which the following products have now been isolated.

1. A sesquiterpene, didymocarpene, $C_{15}H_{24}$.
2. Didymocarpol, $C_{50}H_{100}O_5$, m.p. 76° .
3. Didymocarpenol, $C_{25}H_{42}O$, m.p. 137° .

Of these three products the sesquiterpene is obtained through repeated fractional distillation of the lighter essential oil which distilled over on passing a moderate current of steam through the petroleum ether-soluble neutral portion of the ethereal extract. The two polyterpenes are obtained from the heavier essential oil, which later distill over in a vigorous current of steam. These terpenes are also obtained from the unsaponifiable fraction of the fatty residue, left after steam distillation.

Didymocarpene does not yield a crystalline nitrosyl chloride or nitrosate but may be characterised through the formation with nitrous acid of a crystalline product, m.p. $132-34^\circ$, which appears to be a nitroso-bisnitrosite having the formula $C_{15}H_{23}NO : (ON \cdot NO)_2 \cdot C_{15}H_{24}$. Titration with bromine in the cold points to the presence of two double bonds in the molecule. Apparently didymocarpene belongs to the class of bicyclic sesquiterpenes.

The specific gravity and refractive index of didymocarpene also approximate closely to values required for a bicyclic mono-terpene. Didymocarpol is optically inactive, saturated to bromine, rather inert and stable to alkaline or oxidative degradation. Didymocarpenol contains a single double bond and is strongly *laevorotatory*.

The saturated acids obtained by saponification of the fatty residue appear to consist of lignoceric, behenic, stearic and palmitic acids in nearly equal proportions. Of these the two latter are isolated by repeated fractional crystallisation from dilute alcohol but the former two form an unseparable eutectic mixture whose composition is, however, indicated by its m.p. (75-76°), C-H values and equivalent weight. The unsaturated acids are not further investigated.

Stearic acid was also isolated from the acidic fraction of the original ether extract. None of the other saturated acids could be noted in the free fatty acid fraction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Didymocarpene.—The light greenish yellow oil, obtained on steam distillation of the final filtrates from pedicellin (Siddiqui, *loc. cit.*) was distilled under reduced pressure, when the following fractions were obtained :—

- (1) 75-130°/4 mm., 5 g. of an oil smelling of benzaldehyde.
- (2) 132-40°/4 mm., 44 g. of an odorous straw-coloured oil.
- (3) 140-45°/4 mm., 10 g. deep yellow oil.
- (4) 145-50°/4 mm., 8 g. dark oil.

The residue (2 g.) was rejected.

The benzaldehydic smell of the first fraction was apparently due to contamination with traces of benzaldehyde, produced through hydrolytic splitting of the residual colouring matter, during steam distillation. On redistillation of this fraction and fractions (3) and (4), nearly 20 g. more of fraction (2) were obtained. The combined fractions (2) on rectification finally yielded 64 g. of pure didymocarpene slowly distilling at 135-37°/10 mm. (yield about 1.6% calculated on the weight of the dry leaves).

Didymocarpene is a thin straw-coloured oil with a characteristic pleasant smell. It boils at 136-37°/3 mm. and 147-48°/12 mm. and the b.p. greatly fluctuates with the rate of heating. It showed $[\alpha]_D^{36}, -3.7^\circ$ in 1% absolute alcoholic solution; $d^{34}, 0.8957$; $n^{20}, 1.4988$. [Found: C, 87.9; H, 12.0; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 188. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.2; H, 11.8 per cent. M. W., 204).

Action of Nitrous Acid on Didymocarpene: Didymocarpene-nitroso-bis-nitrosite.—Glacial acetic acid (3 c.c.) was added drop by drop to an ice-cooled mixture of 1 c.c. of oil in petroleum ether and 1 c.c. of concentrated aqueous sodium nitrite. After addition of the acid the bluish coloured mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours, when the blue colour deepened. The petroleum ether layer was then separated, washed well with water, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The dark bluish green residue was dissolved in a small quantity of absolute alcohol and kept in the cold, when it yielded sky-blue prismatic rods which after a few recrystallisations from the same solvent finally melted at 132-34°. (Found after drying to constant weight at 50° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: C, 63.45; H, 8.7; N, 12.1. C₃₀H₄₇O₅N₅ requires C, 62.8; H, 8.3; N, 12.5 per cent).

Action of Bromine on Didymocarpene.—0.49 G. of the substance in chloroform was titrated in the cold with a 3% solution of bromine in chloroform. The absorption of bromine, which was followed with the help of starch iodide paper, stopped after 0.66 g. (3.4 atoms equivalent of bromine) had been added.

Isolation of Didymocarpol and Didymocarpenol.

The residue left after steam distillation of didymocarpene was subsequently subjected to direct heating in a vigorous current of steam. The thick reddish yellow oil which distilled over was taken up in ether, washed, dried and distilled under reduced pressure after removal of the solvent, when the following fractions were obtained.

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| Fraction | 1 | up to 150° /2 mm., a very small quantity of crude didymocarpene. |
| „ | 2 | 155-95° /2 mm. a yellowish red oil (16 g.) |
| „ | 3 | 195-250° /2 mm., a dark red oil (8 g.) |

The residue was rejected. Fractions (2) and (3) crystallised on standing.

Didymocarpol (C₁₀H₂₀O)₅.—After a few crystallisations from alcohol the crystalline mass from fraction (2) was finally obtained as white silky needles, m. p. 76° (yield 0.3% calculated on the weight of the dry leaves). It failed to give an acetyl, benzoyl or a phenylhydrazine derivative and was saturated to bromine. It was stable towards potassium permanganate and could be recovered unchanged after refluxing with alcoholic potash at 140-50° for 2 hours. (Found after drying at 50° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: C, 76.3; H, 12.8; M.W., 750. C₅₀H₁₀₀O₅ requires C, 76.9; H, 12.8 per cent. M. W., 780).

Didymocarpenol, C₂₅H₄₂O.—Fraction (3) also yielded after a few recrystallisations from alcohol snow-white silky needles, m.p. 137°,

yield 0.15%. It failed to give any acetyl, benzoyl or phenylhydrazone derivative but absorbed two atoms equivalent of bromine in chloroform solution. [Found after drying to constant weight at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 83.6; H, 12.0; M. W. (Rasl-), 376. $C_{25}H_{42}O$ requires C, 83.8; H, 11.7 per cent. M. W., 358]. In 1% absolute alcoholic solution it showed $[\alpha]_D^{20}, -65.5^\circ$.

Examination of the Non-volatile Fatty Residue.

Half of the residue, non-volatile in steam, was taken up in ether and shaken with dilute sodium hydroxide. The alkali soluble portion was taken along with the alkali-soluble ethereal mother liquors from pedicin. These together yielded stearic acid, m.p. 69° yield 8 g.

The neutral fraction deposited another crop of pedicellin which was filtered off. The filtrate was freed from the solvent and the residue saponified with 20% alcoholic potash. The acids were separated into the saturated and unsaturated fractions by the lead salt method.

The saturated acid yielded on repeated fractional crystallisation from dilute alcohol 5.5 g. (11% total fatty) of a fraction melting at 75-76°. (Found after drying to constant weight at 50° in *vacuo*: C, 77.6; H, 12.9; Equiv., 351. $C_{23}H_{46}O_2$ requires C, 77.9; H, 12.9 per cent. Equiv., 355).

The residue from the mother-liquors yielded on further fractional crystallisation 2.7 g. of pure stearic acid (m.p. 69°). The most soluble fraction gave 2.3 g. of palmitic acid, m.p. 60-62°. Both these acids showed no depression in m.p. on admixture with authentic specimens of the respective acids.

The unsaponifiable matter yielded further quantities of didymocarpol and didymocarpenol on distillation under reduced pressure and subsequent crystallisations of the respective fractions from alcohol.